

INSTRUCTIONAL CHALLENGES AND COPING INTERVENTION IN THE DISTANCE LEARNING EDUCATION AND TEACHER'S READINESS FOR QUALITY INSTRUCTION: BASIS FOR RESPONSIVE EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the teachers' perceptions on instructional challenges, coping intervention in the implementation of distance learning education and teacher's readiness for quality instructions. The study utilized descriptive correlation design with the sample of 100 elementary school teachers of Tiaong District I Division of Quezon was the respondents. The study took place during the school year 2020-2021. The study gave the priority to technical infrastructure to adjust in the new educational setting, and teachers must be trained in the latest technology to provide quality instructions in the modality of distance learning. Survey questionnaire was administered to the respondents which came up to the following major findings of the study: The study's major findings, priority must be given to technical infrastructure to adapt to new educational settings, and teachers must be trained in technology utilization to provide quality instruction in distance learning. The five challenging indicator were identified. These include geographic location, homeschooling, teaching material development, the learning ability of students, and parental support. As teachers adjust to the new normal and prepare for distance learning, they face challenges that make providing our students with quality instruction difficult. These difficulties should be identified and addressed to help teachers mitigate problems and perform their duties. The geographical location has the highest mean of (4.1200) and (.71351) standard deviation, while the lowest mean is the learning ability of the pupils with (4.0220) and (.70490) standard deviation. Three intervention indicator were identified. These include new educational platforms, innovative teaching strategies, and student connections. Teachers can overcome the barriers encountered during distance learning implementation by using the barriers encountered during distance learning implementation. These enable them to meet the demands of a new learning method while also preparing and fulfilling their duties and responsibilities as facilitators of knowledge. The innovative instructional strategies have the highest mean of (4.1860) and (.60986) standard deviation, while the lowest mean is the new education platform with (4.0340) and (.66852) overall standard deviation. For the teachers' readiness in the delivery of quality education there are three indicators, includes teachers' training workshops, technology utilization and technology infrastructure. Teachers should plan to offer learners multiple opportunities to think about and respond to questions that check their understanding this could be happened if the teachers have intensive training workshops, having knowledge in technology utilization and school have already technology infrastructure. The teachers' training workshops, have the highest mean of (4.2080) and (.59555) standard deviation, while the lowest mean is the technology utilization with (3.9930) and (.71014) overall standard deviation. The salient findings of the study led to the following conclusion: The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between teacher's readiness in the delivery of quality education and instructional challenges

of the distance learning and education is not supported since, based on the findings, the relationship of teacher readiness on the delivery of quality instruction and instructional challenges revealed a substantial correlation between parental support and teacher training and workshops, technology utilization, indicating a considerable correlation or substantial relationship. Since Instructional Challenges of distance learning education have a significant relationship with the teacher's readiness at the 0.01 level of significance (two-tailed), reject the null hypothesis. The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between teacher's readiness in the delivery of quality education and coping interventions in the implementation of distance learning education, according to the findings, there is a substantial correlation between new education platforms and teacher training and workshops, technology utilization, indicating a substantial correlation or substantial resemblance. The hypothesis is rejected because coping interventions in the implementation of distance learning education have a significant relationship with teacher readiness at the 0.01 level of significance (two-tailed), reject the null hypothesis. In addition, the readiness of teachers to deliver quality instruction is significantly and coping interventions in distance learning. School technical infrastructure is needed because we cannot adopt trends in education without upgrading gadgets in schools. There is a need to reinforce the coping intervention in our school to respond to our distance learners' needs and learning ability. In view of aforementioned findings and the conclusion obtain the study, the following recommendation are suggested. As teachers adjust to the new normal and prepare for distance learning, they face challenges that make it challenging to provide quality instruction to our students. These difficulties should be identified and addressed to assist teachers in mitigating problems and carrying out their duties. Teachers may overcome and cope with the barriers encountered during distance learning by utilizing the obstacles encountered during distance learning. These enable them to meet the demands of a new learning modality while also preparing for and carrying out their duties and responsibilities as knowledge facilitator. The school offices and higher authorities may collaborate to address teachers' challenges in implementing distance learning as they transition to normal practices. Teachers should receive relevant training and instructional resources to provide quality education. There is a need for school technical infrastructure because we cannot adopt trends in the educational system without upgrading the gadgets in schools. To meet teaching and learning demands, teachers must rethink and formulate appropriate plans and implement adequate innovative teaching strategies. Teachers must adopt a growth mindset to adapt to the ever-changing possibilities in the education system and step outside of their comfort zone. There is a need to strengthen the coping intervention implemented in our school to respond to the needs and cater to the learning ability of our distance learning students. It is recommended that teachers, school administrators, and parents work collaboratively to deliver quality instruction in distance learning, most likely during these trying times.

Keywords: Instructional Challenges, Coping Intervention, Teacher's Readiness for Quality Instructions